

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OMI****FIRST NAME: KENJI****PROGRAM CODE: LLM-DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Choose the statement that correctly lists the rules of thumb for writing an academic paper as described by EUCLID 2021.

- A) state the main thesis of the paper at the conclusion, B) accept generalities, C) gradually become focused, D) write quickly, E) write comfortably, F) support assertions with data, G) take the views you are discussing seriously, H) do not plagiarize
- A) state the main thesis of the paper throughout the paper, B) stay focused, C) do not lead with such sweeping generalities, D) write clearly, E) do not make the writing boring and clumsy, F) support assertions, G) take the views you are discussing seriously, H) do not plagiarize
- A) state the main thesis of the paper at the beginning, B) stay focused, C) do not lead with such sweeping generalities, D) write by using noble languages, E) do not

- make the writing boring and clumsy, F) support assertions, G) take the views you are discussing seriously, H) do not plagiarize.
- A) state the main thesis of the paper at the beginning, B) stay focused, C) do not lead with such sweeping generalities, D) write clearly, E) do not make the writing boring and clumsy, F) support assertions, G) take the views you are discussing seriously, H) do not plagiarize.** ¹
2. Choose the elements that should be included in the “abstract” of a dissertation as described by Sampson 2017.
- Research questions, methodologies, and recommendations.
- Statement of the problem, research questions, and social significance.**²
- Statement of the problem, methodologies, and references.
- Acknowledgement, research questions, and social significance.
3. Choose the appropriate description of the roles the “discussion” chapter should play in relation to the “literature review” chapter and the “findings” chapters in a dissertation.
- Shows the added value of the findings vis-à-vis the existing literature.**³
- Tests the hypotheses shown in the “literature review” chapter.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course Pack: Period 1. Fourth Edition*, (Bangui: EUCLID University, 2024), 13-15.

² James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 26.

³ Sampson, 56–57.

- Explains the conclusion by building on the “literature review” and the “findings” chapters.
 - Summarize the findings shown by the “findings” chapter.
4. Choose the elements that the “methodology” chapter should include.
- Hypotheses, statement of the problem, and research questions.
 - Definitions of terms, statement of the problem, and social significance.
 - Research questions, discussion, and recommendations.
 - Methodologies, hypotheses, research designs, variables, measures, and participants.**⁴
5. Choose the **incorrect** statement representing the meaning of “measures,” “variables,” and “participants,” all of which are a part of the methodology for writing a dissertation.
- “Variables” mean “variables that a writer includes in the research design that might help the writer to answer the research questions.” For example, participants who have chosen a certain option and participants who have not chosen the option can constitute variables.⁵
 - “Participants” mean “individuals who will provide the data that will be analyzed to answer research questions and test hypotheses.”⁶

⁴ Sampson, 34–53.

⁵ Sampson, 18.

⁶ Sampson, 45.

- “Measures” are “used to assess the performance of variables that are included in research questions and hypotheses.” Examples of “measures” include tests, questionnaires, interviews, observations, analysis of archival data, and documents or computer files.⁷
- “Variables” mean “individuals who will provide the data that will be analyzed to answer research questions and test hypotheses.”**
6. Choose the cases where citing is not necessary, as explained by EUCLID 2021.
- There is no exception at all to the necessity of citation.
- The necessity of citation depends on context.
- When the author uses “signal phrases” such as “. . . point out . . . ,” then citing is not necessary.
- If the knowledge is repeated in many different sources that you have, then you can assume it is common knowledge. For example, “smoking causes lung cancer.”⁸**
7. Choose which of the following citations in a bibliography most correctly applies the note-bibliography style as described by Turabian 2018.

⁷ Sampson, 37.

⁸ EUCLID 2024, 37.

- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth Edition. Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.⁹
- Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth Edition. Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Turabian (2018), *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth Edition.
- Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*.
8. Choose which of the following citations in a bibliography most correctly applies the Bluebook rules for citing a multilateral treaty with a significant date added in Italics.
- Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (1968).
- Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (July 1, 1968).
- Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons, July 1, 1968.
- Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons, *opened for signature, July 1, 1968, 21 U.S.T. 483, 729 U.N.T.S. 161.***¹⁰

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 147–168, 228–241.

¹⁰ Mary Miles Prince, ed., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, Nineteenth Edition (Cambridge: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2010), 189.

9. Choose which of the following citations in a bibliography most correctly applies the Bluebook rules for citing a United Nations General Assembly Resolution, with “¶” meaning the page number.

- G.A. A/RES/47/1, ¶2, Sept. 22, 1992.
- G.A. Res. 47/1, ¶2, U.N. Doc. A/RES/47/1 (Sept. 22, 1992).**¹¹
- U.N. General Assembly Resolutions No. 47.1, page 2, U.N. document No. A/RES/47/1, Sept. 22, 1992.
- U.N. General Assembly Resolutions, ¶2, A/RES/47/1, Sept. 22, 1992.

10. Choose which of the following citations in a bibliography most correctly applies the Bluebook rules for citing a United Nations declaration known by a popular name.

- Universal Declaration of Human Rights, U.N. Doc. A/RES/217(III).
- Universal Declaration of Human Rights, (Dec. 10, 1948).
- Universal Declaration of Human Rights, U.N. Doc. A/RES/217(III) (Dec. 10, 1948).
- Universal Declaration of Human Rights, G.A. Res. 217 (III) A, U.N. Doc. A/RES/217(III) (Dec. 10, 1948).**¹²

¹¹ Prince, 200.

¹² Prince, 200.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Prince, Mary M. *THE BLUEBOOK: A Uniform System of Citation*. Nineteenth Edition. Cambridge: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2010.

James, Sampson P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.